

BIOPLATFORMS
AUSTRALIA

Australian
BioCommons

Australian BioCommons

Strategic Plan

2023 - 2028

V3.0

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1 Introduction

Bioplatforms Australia¹ is enabled by the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS)² to support the Australian life sciences community. It provides access to omics technologies in support of all life science researchers working across human health, agriculture, biodiversity and industry, and makes an integrated capability available to initiatives of breadth and complexity in a way that is not readily achievable through other mechanisms.

Investments by Bioplatforms Australia support much of the current research lifecycle through deep sector engagement with research communities, and are aligned with national strategic research initiatives such as gene and cell therapies, precision medicine, and food security and quality. Existing capabilities in data production, informatics, and human capital in the form of skills and training, and research communities, have ensured Bioplatforms Australia can deeply support many touch points in a researcher's impact journey.³

Bioplatforms Australia have identified that omics have become data-centric digital sciences demanding investment in computing power, data management, software development and deployment, and in expertise not traditionally identified with the biological sciences. Australian BioCommons represents Bioplatforms Australia's response to this digital transition.⁴

¹ <https://bioplatforms.com/>

² <https://www.education.gov.au/ncris>

³ Bioplatforms Australia 2021 Annual Report (pp. 6-7)

https://bioplatforms.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/GH025_Bioplatforms-2021_web.pdf

⁴ From Bioplatforms Australia Strategic Brief 2022

2 Australian BioCommons

Australian BioCommons ([Australian Bioinformatics Commons](https://www.biocommons.org.au/))⁵ is the bioinformatics component of Bioplatforms Australia's research infrastructure platforms⁶ and was established by Bioplatforms Australia in 2019.

It represents a substantial digital capability that extends Bioplatforms Australia's infrastructure and services into the digital domain as part of Bioplatforms Australia's mission to offer comprehensive support for omics data-enabled research. It supplies national bioinformatics research infrastructure to enhance research into the molecular basis of life across all life sciences, including environmental, agricultural, and biomedical science.

Australian BioCommons' overall direction is subject to Bioplatforms Board⁷ approval.

2.1 Purpose

The purpose of Australian BioCommons is to enable Australian life sciences researchers across academia, government and industry, and their collaborators to:

- Understand the molecular basis of life by applying advanced digital research infrastructure, tools, software and training
- Access and apply the bioinformatics tools, methods and reference data that can address national challenges and research questions.

2.2 Vision

Australia's life science research and research translation is enhanced through world class collaborative distributed bioinformatics infrastructure.

World class bioinformatics capabilities empower breakthrough discoveries enabling the realisation of Australia's ambitions in human health, agriculture and biodiversity.

2.3 Mission

Australian BioCommons' mission is to:

- Sustain strategic leadership in the provision and use of bioinformatics and bioscience data infrastructures at a national scale
- Actively support life science research communities with community-scale digital infrastructure, developed and maintained in concert with international peer infrastructures, and tailored to support bioinformatics practice
- Deliver sophisticated analysis capabilities, including software and hardware platforms that underpin world class science

⁵ <https://www.biocommons.org.au/>

⁶ The six research platforms of Bioplatforms Australia are: Genomics, Proteomics, Metabolomics, Synthetic Biology, Catalytic Ideas and Bioinformatics

⁷ The members of the Bioplatforms Australia Board are listed at <https://bioplatforms.com/board/>

- Support digital asset stewardship and management, retention, integration and publication solutions as they evolve
- Provide access to the digital techniques, data and tools that advance Australian capabilities in human, agricultural, and environmental genomics through omics research and its translation
- Accelerate and enhance the impact of bioinformatics by leveraging digital technology advances such as artificial intelligence to significantly lift the productivity and capability of both intensive and occasional users of bioinformatics
- Provide training and support solutions that develop transferable digital research and bioinformatics skills to leverage platforms, tools, services and techniques.

2.4 Values

The values of Australian BioCommons underpin the work we do, and how we do it: Respect, Integrity, Collaboration, Communication, and Innovation.

2.5 NCRIS Principles

Australian BioCommons acknowledges and adheres to all of the NCRIS principles.⁸

- It maximises the capability of the research and innovation system to contribute to economic outcomes, national security, social wellbeing and environmental sustainability
- It is collaborative and planned in a way to provide a network of capabilities that serve the national interest and are aligned to government priorities
- It includes people, skills and knowledge, data, processes and equipment
- Its resources are focused to achieve maximum impact in national priority areas
- It is managed to deliver maximum impact as efficiently as possible. Synergies with complementary and related capabilities drive an ecosystem of support for researchers
- It is widely accessible to researchers and industry across Australia. Barriers to access are as low as practicable
- It enhances participation of researchers in, and provides access to, the international research system
- It is respectful to Indigenous cultures and knowledge, and adopts the principles of Indigenous self-determination, leadership, impact and value, and sustainability and accountability as outlined in the AIATSIS Code of Ethics for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Research.

⁸ 2021 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap, ISBN 978-1-76114-001-3

3 Organisational Design

Feedback received from a wide range of national and international stakeholders consistently identifies a set of key characteristics the Australian BioCommons must have, summarised below.

Characteristics required from a national bioinformatics commons infrastructure		
	Simple to use service platforms	Includes simple to use, web accessible service platforms to which a researcher can bring their research goals, tools, pipelines and data
	Technical platforms for programmatic access	Includes command line accessible platforms to perform large, bespoke or novel data integration and analysis
	Support different expertise levels	For biologists, data-intensive and bioinformatics intensive researchers and bioinformaticians, and beneficial to occasional and intensive users of bioinformatics
	Support across all of life science	For biomedical, environmental and agricultural researchers who apply omics to their research
	Global participation	A mechanism through which Australia can represent its interests and participate in global data and bioinformatics infrastructure endeavours in life sciences
	Researcher and support staff skills development	Includes relevant bioinformatics and systems training and skills development for all user and developer types

Australian BioCommons achieves these characteristics by taking into account where relevant resources already exist, where technologies can be sourced from, as well as the overall complexity of the number of participants in the life science research sector. Success depends on a sustained high level of cooperation between its participants and collaborators. Therefore, a key component of the strategy concerns the arrangements and core practices that create and maintain that cooperation.

Core Practice

Australian BioCommons defines and delivers bioinformatics supporting infrastructure and services of national value to broad communities of researchers across academia, government and industry.

These are implemented through the combined activity of a large number of organisations.

The primary approach is a 'community led design' process as depicted on the left and described below.

Communities and Researchers

Australian BioCommons planning and delivery follows the pattern used in Bioplatforms Australia framework initiatives, focusing on communities of researchers rather than individual researchers or

research projects. This approach brings a new layer of consideration to the resource allocation processes of some Australian BioCommons participant organisations.

Active Feedback Loop

Australian BioCommons prepares and publishes roadmaps of community serving infrastructures, proposes and validates candidate responses with relevant participants, then in consultation with community members selects and implements the highest priority, most practical option. Closing the loop in this way is a strategic contribution to infrastructure planning in life science research.

3.1 Collaboration Principles

The following principles are used to inform high level strategic planning and are taken into account in decision making around prioritisation of resource allocation and management.

Start with National Intent

Australian BioCommons is resourced and governed in the national interest and aligns its activities with the vision and mission of Bioplatforms Australia. Australian BioCommons prioritises activities that benefit the ambitions expressed by national research communities and engages with participants already addressing national outcomes or that are willing to support their achievement.

This intent reflects the desire to integrate Australian BioCommons with the strategy and combined value of Bioplatforms Australia's overall activities and the desire to differentiate the role of Australian BioCommons, with regard to the role of institutions in research infrastructure.

Partner Internationally

A sustained global wave of investment is continuing into bioinformatics infrastructure. Australian BioCommons intends to participate in and contribute to larger critical mass efforts, to reuse and improve rather than build anew, and to 'ride (and actively contribute to) that wave'.

This intent reflects a desire to gain the maximum benefit possible from large global investments to address the bioinformatics challenges present in life science research.

Partner Locally

Australian BioCommons is funded to enable national bioinformatics research infrastructure but cannot support the required nationwide scale of use on its own. Australian BioCommons enables a coordinated approach to this challenge by partnering with other NCRIS supported national digital research infrastructures, state and institutional level bioinformatics centres of expertise and institutional digital infrastructures to provide life science researchers with bioinformatics support, compute and data capacity. Partnering with Australian BioCommons provides an outstanding means for those digital infrastructure capabilities to enhance their impact in the life sciences.

Identify Champions

A key part of Australian BioCommons' mission is to actively support life science research communities with community-scale digital infrastructure. That requires input from community members with a significant level of experience and awareness of national and international initiatives and approaches. Australian BioCommons aims to work with champions within these communities that have that expertise. These may be champions for bioinformatics techniques or their scientific application, and in infrastructure development and supply.

Tailor Infrastructure

Best practice bioinformatics methods constantly evolve, as do the underlying infrastructure requirements. Therefore, Australian BioCommons supports a software and expertise capability that tailors infrastructure for bioinformatics use, allowing researchers to focus on method development and dissemination rather than infrastructure management.

Empower Ambitions

Australian BioCommons develops the talents and aspirations of its staff, collaborators and users. This principle encodes a core tenet of the Australian BioCommons team.

3.2 Coordination

A primary goal of Australian BioCommons is to achieve cohesion across a large number of individuals sourced on a full time or fractional basis from many different organisations. Three layers exist in the approach to strategic direction and operational coordination.

Executive

Australian BioCommons staff report to a small executive team. While members of the executive hold clear and distinct responsibilities, they operate in a collegiate manner so that a shared understanding exists of the issues they address separately and collectively.

The Coordination 'Hub'

A broader team, known as the 'Hub' is composed of the executive team and staff with roles enabling coordination of activities across Australian BioCommons. The Hub meets sufficiently often to ensure its members are aware of, and comprehend, each others' roles and all associated Australian BioCommons activities. A high degree of task flexibility is expected from the Hub team. The operations and communications teams are key components of the Hub.

Participants

At a formal level, participants are organisations. On a day-to-day basis, participants are individuals. Some organisations have a special role in Australian BioCommons as the employers of executive and Hub members. However, in general, a much larger number of participants, both organisations and individuals, are involved in project activities.

Australian BioCommons plans for an increase in its participants and an expected evolution in forms of participation. Each participant's contribution is set out in a contract with the University of Melbourne (acting on behalf of Australian BioCommons).

3.3 Management

Australian BioCommons operates through six centres of activity known as ‘divisions’. Each division is headed by a member of the executive team. While operating in a collegiate manner, divisions have a specific accountability for the strategic direction, stakeholder management, resourcing and delivery of the activities, infrastructure and/or services in their area of expertise.

Division	Focus
Leadership, Management and Operations	Providing the direction and prioritisation of Australian BioCommons activities and the proper operational, legal and financial administration of the activities arising.
Engagement and Community Response	Engaging with the life sciences research community to understand their requirements and advocate their needs for national collaborative bioinformatics research infrastructure.
Platforms and Services	Establishing and operating the bioinformatics platforms and services required by the Australian life sciences research community as informed through community engagement activities.
Human Genome Informatics	Ensuring that global best practice infrastructure for human omics data sharing and analysis is implemented in Australia.
BioCloud	Connecting and harmonising digital resources to make the management and use of infrastructure underpinning bioinformatics more efficient and to enhance the dissemination and application of reference methods and data.
Training and Communications	Facilitating meaningful connections to BioCommons activities and services and raising awareness of the community scale digital infrastructure that we provide. Creating opportunities to develop transferable skills in bioinformatics and supporting the life science community to learn how to use new and existing platforms, tools, services and techniques.

3.4 Priorities

Providing Leadership and Value

Australian BioCommons aims to be the premier bioinformatics investment in the Australian research infrastructure landscape, leading the way in accelerating the uptake of bioinformatics in Australian science and to operate in a way that ensures it is a highly desirable employer for people motivated by that mission.

Engaging Communities

Australian BioCommons aims to actively support life science research communities in Australia with community scale digital infrastructure. The Engagement and Community Response Division undertakes community consultations that generate an understanding of challenges and unmet national bioinformatics infrastructure needs.

The resulting infrastructure roadmaps and reports set out the features of desirable community scale research infrastructure, and enable Australian BioCommons to formulate community endorsed views on what infrastructure is lacking and how essential it is for that gap to be filled.

Establishing and delivering Platforms and Services

The Platform and Services Division focuses on the BioCommons mission to lift the productivity of Australian life scientists. Its goal is to establish, operate and configure online bioinformatics data analysis and digital asset stewardship services based on priorities set by Australian life science research communities (and documented by the Engagement & Community Response Division).

The platforms and services are designed to:

- Simplify researcher access to best practice informatics techniques and reference data
- Provide capability that is better, faster, more economical, more reliable, and more repeatable, than researchers can otherwise readily achieve
- Make it easier for infrastructure providers to supply compute and storage to life scientists.

Enabling Human Genome Informatics

Australian human genomics research and clinical translation currently face significant challenges due to isolated datasets and a lack of a unified national data sharing and analysis strategy. To maintain a competitive edge in global biomedical research, immediate action is necessary.⁹

The Human Genome Informatics Division is enhancing Australia's genomic research through its leadership in the Genomics Uplift for Australia through Research Data Infrastructure At National Scale (GUARDIANS) initiative. This four-year, step change program is a significant new investment aiming to revolutionise how human genomics data is shared and analysed across the country by deploying federated, modular National Digital Research Infrastructure (NDRI). This approach ensures interoperability through well-defined interfaces, facilitating seamless access to data and computational resources.

The GUARDIANS program's strategy incorporates global standards and principles such as GA4GH,¹⁰ FAIR,¹¹ and CARE,¹² under the coordination of a BioCommons-led core services and expertise platform. This alignment aims to enhance the management and analysis of human genomics data throughout its lifecycle, addressing the needs of both biomedical research and industry. The integration of data storage with computational resources will not only boost existing high-performance computing capabilities but also expand research and clinical translation potential through enhanced data analysis and collaborative opportunities.

Establishing and delivering a BioCloud

Over the 2019-2023 period, the challenges in data-intensive life sciences have become clear. Data will be distributed; software will be globally sourced; more dispersed computation will be required for widespread episodic use; users will often be specialists in life sciences and biology rather than computing; and data and software cannot be continuously re-engineered to suit bespoke Australian infrastructure.

⁹

<https://queenslandgenomics.org/qldgenomics-updated/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/NAGIM-Blueprint-v20201010-Final-v1.2.2.pdf>

¹⁰ <https://www.ga4gh.org/our-products/>

¹¹ <https://www.go-fair.org/>

¹² <https://www.gida-global.org/>

In response, the BioCloud Division targets three key improvements. The first concerns the ability for researchers to work with data, tools and workflows in a research and infrastructure context above the computational ‘cores, stores and plumbing’ components. The goal is that researchers are able to seamlessly work within agreed community rights and privileges, utilising international data exchange standards to couple analysis engines with data assets, and then execute reference and bespoke workflows over that assembled resource. The second relates to growth in the accessible corpus of data, to be achieved by integrating disparate data services and ensuring researchers can easily work with those services. The third relates to an expansion in the fraction of national and institutional infrastructure that accommodates BioCloud's access and bioinformatics readiness, through their policies and configurations.

Delivering Bioinformatics Training

In the era of ‘big’ biological data, developing the bioinformatics competencies is considered to be one of the most significant challenges facing the global life science research community.¹³

Australian BioCommons enables the critical workforce transition required for life science research excellence by creating opportunities to develop transferable skills in bioinformatics and skills in using available platforms, tools, services and techniques. Strong collaborations with the national network of bioinformatics training providers, national research infrastructures, and strategic global partners enable the delivery of best practice, practical and accessible bioinformatics training events and learning resources. The Training team also uplifts bioinformatics trainers in Australia through the National Bioinformatics Training Cooperative¹⁴. This community brings together trainers and training providers to create new opportunities to deliver collaborative events and valuable training resources.

Exploiting Artificial Intelligence

A call for papers for a special issue of Elsevier’s Information and Organization journal (2024)¹⁵ highlighted the rapid growth of emerging yet transformational digital technologies, as follows:

“Organisations of the 21st century face a seemingly indeterminable array of emerging digital technologies, which are radically novel and rapidly evolving, with profound transformative potential”, “current emerging digital technologies, including artificial intelligence, blockchain, quantum computing, 5G, 3D printing, smart manufacturing and energy, genomics and precision medicine, drones, augmented reality, and autonomous vehicles are transforming markets and societies, as well as the very core of how we organise. These and other technologies generate such an impact because they are increasingly ‘autonomous’ and ‘intelligent’, which complements, augments, and even replaces human action”.

Australian BioCommons will engage and understand the manner in which artificial intelligence augments analysis and data capabilities but also the manner in which it complements, augments or replaces human action in research and specifically the practice of bioinformatics within research.

Achieving Organisational Excellence

The implementation of the Australian BioCommons confronts a fundamental organisational challenge: it intends to operate as a coherent activity while being constructed through a large number of bilateral arrangements between many participant organisations.

¹³ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41587-023-01891-9>

¹⁴ <https://www.biocommons.org.au/training-cooperative>

¹⁵

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/information-and-organization/about/call-for-papers#organizing-for-emerging-digital-technologies-the-good-the-bad-the-ugly>

This challenge is addressed by the Operations team who establish and oversee all aspects of the Australian BioCommons operating structure (encompassing legal, finance, human resources, administration, research administration, internal communications and other matters). The team develops and delivers an administrative practice that is inclusive of all Australian BioCommons' funders and participants and their specific policies and practices.

Delivering Impactful Communications

The Communications team creates novel events and engagements that facilitate meaningful connections to Australian BioCommons activities and services. The team's goals are to raise awareness beyond the project and to improve participation by life science research infrastructure stakeholders and to raise awareness and improve adoption by life science researchers.

4 Implementation

4.1 Broad Participation

Australian BioCommons' strategy hinges on the enlistment of many contributors that apply their own resources to expand its activities. This is necessary if Australian BioCommons is to serve its target research base, given its scale in comparison to the scale of that research base.

Australian BioCommons' participants fall into six broad categories which have distinct characteristics.

Nodes As of Q1 2026, four Nodes, the University of Melbourne, the Queensland Cyber Infrastructure Foundation (QCIF)¹⁶, the University of Sydney's Sydney Informatics Hub¹⁷ and the University of Queensland¹⁸ provide backbone arrangements that underpin the durability of Australian BioCommons. These entities either employ, second or host staff who have key roles within Australian BioCommons. Such staff are normally assigned to the Australian BioCommons project full time, where Australian BioCommons supports direct costs and participants support indirect costs. Nodes also engage across other participant categories as opportunities arise.

Delivery Partners Delivery partners provide an important combination of long term roles required to support Australian BioCommons' activities (fractional or full time) and/or long term access to requisite infrastructure and services. Australian BioCommons and its delivery partners share direct costs and the partners support indirect costs. Delivery partners also engage as project participants, as opportunities arise. AARNet,¹⁹ NCI²⁰ and Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre (Pawsey)²¹ are examples of delivery partners.

Project Participants Project participants are organisations that engage in focused projects for a fixed term and provide personnel and infrastructure resources as agreed in a project plan. Australian BioCommons and project participants share direct costs, with

¹⁶ <https://www.qcif.edu.au/>

¹⁷ <https://www.sydney.edu.au/research/facilities/sydney-informatics-hub.html>

¹⁸ <https://research-support.ug.edu.au/resources-and-support/facilities-and-infrastructure/data-science-collaborative-research-platform>

¹⁹ <https://www.aarnet.edu.au/>

²⁰ <https://nci.org.au/>

²¹ <https://pawsey.org.au/>

project participants supporting indirect costs. The Children’s Cancer Institute, QIMR-Berghofer, Garvan Institute, Monash University and AGRF are examples of project partners from the 2019-2023 phase.

Technology Developers	Australian BioCommons’ co-development principle leads to the use of internationally sourced research infrastructure technologies and systems. By contributing improvements to these technologies, and engaging in a forward thinking dialogue with their providers, Australian BioCommons leverages a much larger (and global) effort towards its mission than it contributes itself. The Galaxy Platform ²² and Gen3 Platform ²³ are key examples.
Service Suppliers	A number of fee-for-service suppliers (e.g. Microsoft Azure, AWS, Seqera, Softberry etc.) provide specific software licences, expertise and/or pay as you go infrastructure to Australian BioCommons. Their products are often used as is.
Community Contributors	The participation of researcher and research infrastructure community members, as well as life science practitioners, is critical to engagement and outreach activities at Australian BioCommons. Community contributors also voluntarily assist in the delivery of National Bioinformatics Training Cooperative events and resources, and participate in domain-specific research community consultations and meetings.

Australian BioCommons also participates as a collaborator or project member in services and infrastructures developed and deployed by other organisations when they fulfil specific research capabilities that add value to its mission. The Australian Reference Genome Atlas (ARGA)²⁴, by the Atlas of Living Australia²⁵, and the Australian Cardiovascular disease Data Commons (ACDC)²⁶, by the Baker Heart and Diabetes Institute, are two examples.

4.2 International Co-development

The simple numerics of global research and research infrastructure spending means that as research software and infrastructure grows in scale, capacity and complexity, more of Australia’s research software and infrastructure will be influenced, developed or co-developed with international interests.

The challenges are twofold:

- To be close enough to the forefront to influence development of features that Australia needs
- To be sufficiently informed to accelerate Australia’s adoption and exploitation of such features as they mature.

Australian BioCommons has developed the following approaches to these challenges:

1. Engaging and collaborating with other infrastructure providers that deliver their equivalent of the BioCommons value proposition to their researchers, specifically ELIXIR²⁷ and peer national infrastructures such as the UK’s BioFAIR²⁸ or Sweden’s NBIS.²⁹

²² <https://galaxyproject.org/>

²³ <https://gen3.org/>

²⁴ <https://app.arga.org.au/>

²⁵ <https://www.ala.org.au/>

²⁶ <https://acdc.baker.edu.au/>

²⁷ <https://elixir-europe.org/>

²⁸ <https://biofair.uk/>

²⁹ <https://nbis.se/>

2. Focusing on mission critical software tools, and applies sufficient expertise and value to influence development outcomes; a position now achieved with Galaxy³⁰ and Gen3.³¹
3. Deploying internationally developed software products or standards which have broad application and influencing the development of these products as early adopters. Examples include Seqera³² and technologies such as Beacon, TRS and DRS from GA4GH.³³

4.3 National Co-delivery

Many life science researchers working on data intensive and compute bound challenges require significantly more digital resources than are available to them through existing channels.

To enable bioinformatics for all life science researchers, Australian BioCommons engages with a range of institutional, national and commercial suppliers of digital research infrastructure. The goal is to better deliver the tools and training the research users of bioinformatics require.

Compute

Australian BioCommons delivers computational capabilities to better support bioinformatics by engaging with suppliers of digital research infrastructure in the following ways:

1. Supporting access to very significant high end resources such as leading edge graphic processing units (GPUs) and multi-terabyte memory machines for researchers on call, as needed, and in a highly accessible and cost effective way through Galaxy Australia.³⁴
2. Streamlining access to scalable resources for command line users, currently implemented with NCI and Pawsey, through ABLeS - the 'Australian BioCommons Leadership Share'.³⁵
3. Developing command line environments tailored to the needs of Australian life science communities, deployed at the digital research infrastructures they use.

Tools and Workflows

Australian BioCommons improves access to bioinformatics tools and workflows in four ways:

1. Providing the Galaxy Australia service in collaboration with multiple national bioinformatics and infrastructure partners (QCIF, the University of Queensland, the University of Melbourne, AARNet, NCI, Pawsey, ARDC Nectar Research Cloud³⁶). Galaxy Australia is one of the founding instances of the global usegalaxy.* network, an international, open access, bioinformatics service. usegalaxy.* makes thousands of tools easily and readily available to hundreds of thousands of researchers worldwide.
2. Working with international tool and workflow repositories (e.g. WorkflowHub,³⁷ bio.tools,³⁸ Biocontainers³⁹) to create and re-use well described versions of tools and workflows that are portable and readily available, and to work towards a future automated distribution service.
3. Working with high end HPC providers (NCI, Pawsey) to ensure that highly optimised and tuned versions of high use bioinformatics tools and workflows are available to their user base.

³⁰ <https://galaxyproject.org/>

³¹ <https://gen3.org/>

³² <https://seqera.io/>

³³ <https://www.ga4gh.org/our-products/#>

³⁴ <https://usegalaxy.org.au/>

³⁵ <https://www.biocommons.org.au/ables>, Gustafsson, O. J. R., Al Bkhetan, Z., Francis, R., & Manos, S. (2023). Enabling national step changes in bioinformatics through ABLeS, the Australian BioCommons Leadership Share (3.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10139651>

³⁶ <https://ardc.edu.au/services/ardc-nectar-research-cloud/>

³⁷ <https://workflowhub.eu/>

³⁸ <https://bio.tools/>

³⁹ <https://biocontainers.pro/>

4. Developing a national bioinformatics workflow deployment and monitoring service based on the commercial Seqera Platform⁴⁰ product to run, manage, and monitor the execution of Nextflow workflows across institutional, national and commercial cloud platforms.

Data

Australian BioCommons improves data accessibility and use in three ways:

1. Implementing, operating and maintaining a long term data repository for data whose generation Bioplatforms Australia sponsors (Bioplatforms Australia Data Portal).⁴¹
2. Implementing a data discovery solution for omics data from Australian relevant species operating across onshore and offshore omic data holdings (Australian Reference Genome Atlas - ARGAs)⁴² in collaboration with the Atlas of Living Australia.
3. Pursuing national federations of human genomic and other data holdings for specific applications, such as in omics informed medical research.⁴³

Australian BioCommons also has an ambition to improve Australian life science researchers' ability to publish data to core global data repositories of record, and to better access and utilise data from many data services.⁴⁴

Training

Australian BioCommons delivers training events and resources in partnership with Australia's best universities and research institutions, and convenes Australia's National Bioinformatics Training Cooperative.⁴⁵ The cooperative is interwoven with international bioinformatics training partners and is championed by leading bioinformatics training institutions from around Australia.

4.4 Underpinning Arrangements

Formal arrangements instantiating and monitoring Australian BioCommons are as follows:

Governance

The scope, purpose and overall activities of Australian BioCommons are defined in funding agreements between the Commonwealth Department of Education and Bioplatforms Australia. Consequently the Board of Bioplatforms Australia has overall governance accountability.

Legal

Australian BioCommons is not a legal entity. It is established through a contract between Bioplatforms Australia Ltd. and the University of Melbourne. The University of Melbourne in turn, executes fit-for-purpose contracts with organisations participating or contributing to Australian BioCommons activities.

Delivery

The University of Melbourne is accountable to Bioplatforms Australia for the successful delivery of Australian BioCommons. The performance of Australian BioCommons is monitored and reported through Key Performance Indicators specified between the University of Melbourne and Bioplatforms Australia, and as updated by NCRIS from time to time.

⁴⁰ <https://www.biocommons.org.au/seqera-platform>

⁴¹ <https://data.bioplatforms.com/>

⁴² <https://app.arga.org.au/>

⁴³ <https://www.biocommons.org.au/human-genome-informatics-initiative>

⁴⁴ <https://www.biocommons.org.au/data-repositories>

⁴⁵ <https://www.biocommons.org.au/training-cooperative>

Executive

The Australian BioCommons executive team has one Director and five Associate Directors, supported by dedicated administrative specialists.

Human Resources

Australian BioCommons associated staff are employed through numerous organisations. The legal, remuneration and occupational health and safety aspects of personnel management remain the responsibility of each employing organisation. Line management within Australian BioCommons is implemented so that all roles have an Australian BioCommons related supervisor, who acts in concert with a nominated line manager in the employing organisation (if different), to complete all performance and career development functions.

Financial

Funding to support agreed Australian BioCommons activities is transferred to participants in accordance with contracts between relevant parties. Participant organisations are expected to manage those funds with due diligence and in accordance with their own financial policies.

5 Resourcing

Bioplatforms Australia has provided the following funding to Australian BioCommons:

- Initial Phase, 2018 to 2023, \$20M
- Current Phase, 2023 to 2028, \$55M

The initial phase of funding enabled establishment of the foundational infrastructure and services of Australian BioCommons. The services, training programs and platforms established during this phase are highly utilised and growing steadily, measured by usage statistics, citations and user satisfaction ratings. The current phase of funding will enable Australian BioCommons to continue to grow its team along with a community of national and international infrastructure and research partners, who collectively spearhead innovative solutions.

The current phase is supported by funds from the Australian Government (NCRIS) and through granting opportunities such as the Medical Research Future Fund (MRFF).⁴⁶

Three strategic engagements have also led to significant new funding allocations in the BioCommons current (2023-28) phase through the 2023 NCRIS Research Infrastructure Investment Plan.⁴⁷

- Integrated analysis platforms for omics research through the development of a 'BioCloud' - a unified set of 'research context aware' digital services tailored to meet the requirements of life sciences researchers to work with molecular biological data, using bioinformatics tools and workflows on a variety of infrastructures.
- Foundational infrastructure for accelerating biodiversity research and conservation (Australian Tree of Life Data Laboratories) bringing together national omics data with multidisciplinary data (environment, climate, trait) and connecting these to build a portfolio of transparent and repeatable analytical tools supporting deeply informed biodiversity and biosecurity management decisions.
- A translational human omics data infrastructure program (GUARDIANS) to drive a step change to cutting-edge national digital research infrastructure and unlock Australia's potential

⁴⁶ <https://www.health.gov.au/our-work/medical-research-future-fund>

⁴⁷ <https://www.biocommons.org.au/news/new-funding-2023>

in human omics research through the provision of secure, scalable, and integrated data and analytics platforms.

Generally, the NCRIS funding is matched by Australian BioCommons contributors so that the total investment is expected to average over \$20M a year. Australian BioCommons' contributors successfully source some of that additional resource from institutional and state government infrastructure support funding pools. Substantial support also arises from:

- In-kind contribution of community time in defining, shaping, trialling and improving the research serving infrastructure and research serving services supplied through Australian BioCommons
- Offshore investment in the technologies that Australian BioCommons deploys and co-develops with its technology partners
- Provision of computational resource by the University of Melbourne, QCIF, University of Queensland Research Computing Centre,⁴⁸ NCI, Pawsey and the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud
- Trainer and Facilitator time and effort towards our Bioinformatics Training Cooperative and broader Bioinformatics Training Program⁴⁹
- Institutional indirect costs such as campus infrastructure, and legal, financial and HR systems.

6 Background Factors

The framing of Australian BioCommons, as set out in its 2019-23 Strategic Plan,⁵⁰ continues to resonate with research needs.

6.1 Researcher Numbers

The total pool of Australian publicly funded researchers and higher degree students is of the order of ~100,000, based on tables from the Australian Bureau of Statistics (ABS) for 2022-23.⁵¹

Category	FTE
Researchers	38,346
Technicians + Other Staff	23,260
Higher Degree Students	44,327
TOTAL	105,933

These cover the higher education, government and private non-profit sectors, each supporting 77%, 15% and 8% of publicly funded researchers respectively.

ABS data suggests about 30% of public research *funding* is bioscience related, of which approximately 70% is in biomedicine, 15% in agriculture and 15% in biodiversity.

⁴⁸ <https://rcc.uq.edu.au/>

⁴⁹ <https://www.biocommons.org.au/biocommons-training>

⁵⁰ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.4001193>

⁵¹ See <https://www.abs.gov.au/statistics/industry/technology-and-innovation>

6.2 Researcher Categories

The categories of life science researcher identified in the 2019-23 Strategic Plan remain relevant:

1. **Biology-focused bioscience researchers:** occasional users of bioinformatics tools.
2. **Data-intensive bioscience researchers:** individuals where bioinformatics analysis of omics data is a critical contributor to their research outcomes.
3. **Bioinformatics-intensive bioscience researchers:** individuals where their research is fully dependent on bioinformatics analyses.
4. **Bioinformaticians:** individuals whose research is exclusively focused on bioinformatics technique, algorithm or tool development.

Nearly two thirds of researchers in life science are estimated to be in category 1, about 20% in category 2 and about 10% across categories 3 and 4. Bioinformatics leaders in peer research countries confirm a similar distribution.

However, while it was thought five years ago (see 2019-23 Strategic Plan) that Australian BioCommons would assist the migration of most researchers to ever more intense bioinformatics (i.e. progressing from Category 1, to Categories 2 and 3 etc above), current thinking is centred on better supporting researchers in each category.

6.3 Service Categories

The consultation study report to Bioplatfroms Australia, which proposed the establishment of Australian BioCommons in 2017, suggested that the Australian bioscience community would benefit from the following capabilities that were judged at the time to be missing or needing improvement.

1. Simple-to-use service platforms to which a researcher can bring their research goals, tools, pipelines and data, that seamlessly integrate with all the resources they might need
2. Technical platforms on which data assemblies can more easily occur and be sustained by interest groups within and across institutions
3. Collaboration platforms which can support and derive benefit from national scale data investment
4. A means by which omics data types can be included in data integration efforts with other domains

The proposition was that each of those separate capabilities could be targeted by specific research infrastructure and related services created and supplied by Australian BioCommons and its participants. In practice, Australian BioCommons initially focused on developing services related to 1) and 2), creating a 'methods commons' in contrast to a 'data commons'.

However, in the lead up to the 2023-28 funding commitments, activities supporting multi-use data have emerged. These include the Australian Apollo Service⁵² and the Australian Reference Genome Atlas (ARGA),⁵³ both of which are related to 3), and more recently, the Australian Cardiovascular disease Data Commons (ACDC)⁵⁴ which relates to 4). The grand vision of a genomics-driven

⁵² <https://www.biocommons.org.au/apollo>

⁵³ <https://www.biocommons.org.au/arga>

⁵⁴ <https://www.biocommons.org.au/acdc>

Australian 'tree-of-life' encompassing all the reference genomes of the species in Australia⁵⁵ also relates to 4).

The 2017 consultation study report also confirmed three encompassing challenges. While these are very important to bioscience, they take effect within broader contexts.

5. The simple retention of data at the volumes expected represents a very significant challenge as does the curation of data at the scale envisaged. This reaches to the purposes of data retention beyond immediate research, such as substantiating research results over appropriate periods, and would be expected to engage institutional and national investments in relevant infrastructure.
6. An earlier consultancy on bioinformatics undertaken by Bioplatforms in 2015 highlighted the key issues of skills. The observation is that the rates of change are so high that specific attention to skilling and reskilling the research workforce is needed. No section of the bioscience workforce is immune from the rate of change effects. Again this is a community wide problem that needs addressing for many reasons beyond the delivery of the infrastructure elements proposed in 1) to 4).
7. There is a clear momentum developing globally towards the establishment of large genomic collections, outside of the basic data repositories, that integrate and curate genomic data with other data types. A means to engage government sponsored national scale 'omics data initiatives needs to be established as well as a means to represent Australia in an agreement context internationally where appropriate.

In response, in relation to 5) and 7) the Bioplatforms Australia Data Portal retains primary data where its creation was specifically sponsored by Bioplatforms, and Australian BioCommons energises 6) through a national training cooperative.

⁵⁵ <https://bioplatforms.com/news/australian-tree-of-life-informatics-capability/>